

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids. Part XI. The Infrared Spectra of N-Arylhydroxamic Acids

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The most characteristic bands associated with the hydroxamic acid functional grouping,

are due to the (O–H) and (C = O) stretching vibrations and these can be assigned rather unambiguously. The (C–N) and (N–O) stretching vibrations and (O–H) deformation vibrations can be assigned with less certainty because of overlapping by several other modes of vibrations and because of the non-availability of systematic data on the assignment of these bands in the infrared spectra of hydroxamic acids.

The frequencies of absorption bands associated with (O–H), (C = O) and (N–O) stretching vibrations are given in Table I. The assignment of various bands is briefly discussed below.

(O–H) *Stretching Vibrations*: In the N-arylhydroxamic acids examined here the band due to (O–H) stretching vibrations has been assigned in the region between 3280 cm⁻¹ and 3070 cm⁻¹ (Table I). It is well known that the absorption bands due to (O–H) stretching vibrations, when free, appear around 3600 cm⁻¹; hydrogen bonding shifts these bands to lower frequencies¹⁻⁴. It thus implies that these hydroxamic acids are involved in strong hydrogen bonding.

Most of the changes in the (O–H) stretching vibrations are mainly due to the ability of acidic hydrogen of the hydroxyl group to form “hydrogen bonds” with electron rich atoms. In hydroxamic acids, the acidic (O–H) group is placed in a very close proximity of the polar carbonyl group, = C^{δ+} = O^{δ-}. This situation is highly favourable for the formation of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding of the type given below.

Thus, the formation of strong hydrogen bond causes a large shift in the absorption band to lower frequencies, of the order of 500 cm⁻¹, and may be ascribed to the resonance

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TABLE I

Infrared Absorption Spectra of N-Arylhydroxamic Acids

Compd. No.	Hydroxamic acid	Frequency cm^{-1}		
		$\nu\text{O-H}$	$\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$	$\nu\text{N-O}$
1	N-Phenyl- <i>o</i> -fluorobenzo-	3170	1628	938
2	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>o</i> -fluorobenzo-	3160	1620	—
3	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>o</i> -fluorobenzo-	3150	1630	935
4	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -fluorobenzo-	3100	1620	928
5	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -chlorobenzo-	3175	1600	920
6	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>o</i> -bromobenzo-	3180	1610	920
7	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>m</i> -bromobenzo-	3180	1600	920
8	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -bromobenzo-	3100	1615	930
9	N-Phenyl- <i>o</i> -iodobenzo-	3202	1625	923
10	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>o</i> -nitrobenzo-	3125	1639	926
11	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>o</i> -nitrobenzo-	3165	1613	933
12	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>m</i> -nitrobenzo-	3289	1600	917
13	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -nitrobenzo-	3125	1626	935
14	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-3,5-dinitrobenzo-	3125	1626	917
15	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-3,5-dinitrobenzo-	3125	1639	921
16	N-Phenyl- <i>m</i> -methoxybenzo-	3260	1610	917
17	N- <i>o</i> -Tolyl- <i>m</i> -methoxybenzo-	3160	1610	938
18	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>m</i> -methoxybenzo-	3170	1620	935
19	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>m</i> -methoxybenzo-	3240	1610	935
20	N-Phenyl-2,4-dimethoxybenzo-	3125	1613	925
21	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-2,4-dimethoxybenzo-	—	1605	925
22	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-2,4-dimethoxybenzo-	3100	1600	930
23	N-Phenyl-2-naphtho-	3250	1625	910
24	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-2-naphtho-	3190	1630	941
25	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-2-naphtho-	3175	1608	935
26	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -chlorophenoxyaceto-	3270	1625	910
27	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -chlorophenoxyaceto-	3260	1620	915
28	N-Phenyl-2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyaceto-	3175	1639	913
29	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyaceto-	3125	1613	909
30	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyaceto-	3125	1639	909
31	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-myristo-	3180	1630	921
32	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-palmito-	3180	1630	921
33	N-Phenyl-stearo-	3145	1626	910
34	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-stearo-	3175	1630	921
35	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-stearo-	3160	1623	909
36	N-Phenyl-beheno-	3175	1634	909
37	N- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-beheno-	3175	1632	909

Note: Spectra were recorded as nujol mulls except for compounds nos. 1-9, 16-22, 26, 27, 31, 32, 34 and 35 which were studied as KBr pellets.

stabilization. A consequence of this resonance stabilization should be to lower the force constant of the carbon-oxygen bond and to increase the contribution of single bond form, thereby causing a fall in the frequency of the ($C=O$) stretching vibrations. That this is so, will be seen in the latter part of this discussion.

The assignment of bands, made here is supported by the work of Baumgarten⁵, Hadzi⁶ and others⁷⁻¹². The hydrogen bonding is of intramolecular type and is confirmed by "solution studies" made by other workers^{8,13}.

(C=O) Stretching Vibrations: In the N-arylhydroxamic acids examined here the ($C=O$) stretching bands are assigned in the region between 1640 and 1600 cm^{-1} . This assignment is made with reference to the spectra of amides, anilides and unsubstituted hydroxamic acids. It is well known that the amide I band is primarily due to $\nu C=O$ ^{14,15}. In unsubstituted amides, $RCONH_2$, this band is located between 1690 and 1650 cm^{-1} , while in substituted amides, $RCONHR$, it is observed between 1680 and 1650 cm^{-1} ,^{15,16}. In unsubstituted hydroxamic acids like benzohydroxamic acid it is assigned at 1667 cm^{-1} by Farha¹¹, and at 1661 cm^{-1} by Usova¹⁷. Orville-Thomas assigned this band at 1647 cm^{-1} in formohydroxamic acid¹⁸. Mathis¹⁹ assigned this band in benzo-, propiono-, cinnamo-, and *p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic acids at 1640 ± 30 cm^{-1} .

The position of ($C=O$) stretching band is much influenced by molecular structure and is generally shifted to lower frequencies^{20,21}. Thus the hydrogen bonding lowers $\nu C=O$ by 10-45 cm^{-1} ,^{16,20,21}. Conjugation of the carbonyl group with $C=C$ lowers the absorption band by about 30 cm^{-1} for the first conjugation. When an aromatic ring is directly attached to the carbon atom of the carbonyl group, the frequency shift of the carbonyl group is generally, less than that occurring with a full double bond in conjugation. The substituents of the aromatic ring and the ring strain also lower the carbonyl absorption frequency^{4,15,20}. Thus, the range of ($C=O$) absorption 1640-1600 cm^{-1} , observed here for N-arylhydroxamic acids is in fair agreement with the above referred empirical rules.

(N-O) Stretching Vibrations: In N-arylhydroxylamines this band appears around 915 cm^{-1} ,^{22,23}. In aromatic hydroxamic acids such as BHA it appears here 900 cm^{-1} ,^{19,9} In several oximes this band appears at around 950 cm^{-1} ,^{8,18,24}. It therefore appears reasonable to look for this band in the 950 to 900 cm^{-1} region. A reference sharp band at 920 ± 20 cm^{-1} may be attributed to ($N-O$) stretching mode. The band is rather conspicuous in all spectra examined here. This assignment is supported by the recent work of Pilipenko¹⁰ who assigned this band in the spectra of PBHA and N-phenyl-2-furohydroxamic acid at 915 and 912 cm^{-1} , respectively. Earlier Hadzi⁶ assigned this band at 890 cm^{-1} in PBHA.

It may be noted that this portion of the infrared spectrum contains several aromatic and other bands and hence caution must be exercised in assigning ($N-O$) band.

EXPERIMENTAL

The synthesized N-arylhydroxamic acids^{25,26,27} were recrystallized from suitable solvent and dried over P_2O_5 under vacuum prior to use.

The infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model 221 or Perkin-Elmer Model 137 Spectrophotometers as KBr pellets or as mulls in nujol.

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